

Design of a Kelvin cell acoustic metamaterial

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Abstract

Advancements in 3D print technology now allows the printing of structured acoustic absorbent materials at appropriate microscopic scale and sample sizes. Optimisation of parameter sets associated with a Kelvin Cell structure have the potential to develop various metabehaviours in the associated acoustic responses. The repeatability of the fundamental cell unit also provide a route for the development of viable macro models to simulate built up structures based on detailed models of the individual cell units. This paper describes a process to model, print and test of such a sample. Manufacturing restraints will initially guide the optimised design. Micro to macro models based on a single cell structure which are cross checked against a full visco thermal acoustic finite element model of the individual cell. A macro model based on a reduced lossy helmholtz system is then used to predict the absorptive response response under normal incidence and checked against a manufactured sample under experimental test.

1 Introduction

It is generally accepted that viable working models of the acoustic behaviour of certain classes of acoustically absorbent materials can be adequately predicted by empirical models calibrated by for example Delaney, Bazely, Miki [1]. By these models the absorptive parameters can be expressed as frequency (ω), flow resistivity (σ), density $\rho_0(\omega, \sigma)$ and bulk modulus $K(\omega, \sigma)$ with the acoustical modelling then proceeding using an equivalent fluid obeying a lossy Helmholtz equation. Due to the statistical nature of the solidification process it is usually necessary to supplement the modelling with some static flow tests to determine σ or alternatively to estimate this using reduced models in the case of fibrous materials at least to estimate σ from the individual fibre geometries themselves. A 3D meta structure, on the other hand, generates a regular repeated geometric structure which allows the modelling of the losses though the use of an equivalent hydraulic radius and a companion equivalent cylindrical tube model. Bezemer-Krijnen et al [2] successfully demonstrate this approach on a stacked sphere structure.

In this paper we analyse a single open kelvin cell using a full visco-thermal model and then determine the equivalent hydraulic radius by comparison with a lossy helmholtz model of the the same structure. Once r is determined we can then build an efficient hardbacked model of a manufacturable system 10 cells deep and estimate the absorbency. This is finally compared with experimental test results.

1.1 Background models

The lossy acoustics in a fine absorptive medium can be modelled by linearised visco thermal fluid mechanical models. These are governed by the equation system given for example in Nijhof *et al.* [3]

$$\rho_0(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) + j\omega\rho = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$j\omega\rho_0\mathbf{v} = -\nabla p + \mu(\nabla \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v} + \frac{1}{3}\nabla\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \quad (2)$$

$$j\omega\rho_0 C_p T = \kappa\Delta T + j\omega p \quad (3)$$

$$p = R(\rho_0 T + \rho T_0) \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{v} , p , ρ , T , μ , R , ρ_0 , T_0 , κ , C_p and ω are the acoustic harmonic velocity, pressure, density, temperature, dynamic viscosity, gas constant, static density, static temperature, thermal conductivity, specific heat at constant pressure and angular frequency. In the above formulation the fluid is assumed to be Stoksian. A finite element model implementing the above was constructed using a mixed weak formulation following [3] and Zienkiewicz *et al.* [4] which can present the system in the matrix form

$$[\mathbf{K} + j\omega\mathbf{M}]\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{F} \quad (5)$$

As the density variable may be eliminated using the equation of state, Equation 4, each node will have five degrees of freedom including three velocity components, temperature and pressure stored in \mathbf{a} . The forcing vector \mathbf{F} then models boundary pressure loads, material injection and heat flux. \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{M} were constructed following the procedures for mixed formulations outlined in [4]. In order to develop a stable mixed model it is critical to use shape functions of one order less for the pressure and its weighting functions. In this work quadratic 10 noded tetrahedral elements were used with linear functions for pressure and quadratic functions for the velocity and temperature. The redundant mid side nodal pressure degrees of freedom were decoupled from the formulation and 2nd order volumetric integrations were used.

The general equation system in Section 1.1 has also shown itself to be amenable over the frequency ranges of interest to efficient Padé type frequency sweeps such as the WCAWE method proposed by Slone *et al.* [5]. In the cell system equation needed only to be solved at a single frequency with extrapolation using derivatives up to order 25 being adequate to cover the frequency range,

1.2 From Micro to Macro visco thermal modelling

Solution of the full system equations is extremely expensive and precludes the solutions for structures of conjoined cell models of practical interest. Unfortunately the equation systems themselves are poorly conditioned and there does not seem to be a viable preconditioning method reported in the literature at this time to enable iterative solution approaches. Therefore full visco-thermal simulations of absorptive labyrinthine structures of the scale needed for the application projects will not be viable. Clearly a model reduction strategy such as, for example, the Low Reduced Frequency approaches whereby a simple Helmholtz model is formulated enabling the simulation of much more extensive structures with the lossy elements modelled as boundary loads. The losses themselves are modelled approximately using equivalent cylindrical duct losses following, for example, Allard and Atalla [6]. The link between more complex structures such as stacked spheres by Bezemer-Krijnen *et al.* [2] is through the use of an “hydraulic radius” r . This is given by

$$r = \frac{2V}{A} \quad (6)$$

where V is the volume of a single acoustic cell entrapped by the spheres and A is the wetted surface area. Using the corrections for averaged density $\rho(\omega)$ and bulk modulus $K(\omega)$ in cylindrical bores provided for

Figure 1: Kelvin Cell

example by [6] which can be summarised as

$$\rho(\omega) = \frac{\rho_0}{G(\omega)} \quad (7)$$

$$K(\omega) = \frac{K_0}{\Gamma(\omega)} \quad (8)$$

where

$$s = r \sqrt{\frac{\omega \rho_0}{\mu}} \quad (9)$$

$$B = \sqrt{\frac{\mu C_p}{\kappa}} \quad (10)$$

$$G(\omega) = 1 - \frac{2J_1(s\sqrt{-j})}{s\sqrt{-j}J_0(s\sqrt{-j})} \quad (11)$$

$$\Gamma(\omega) = 1 + \frac{2(\gamma - 1)J_1(Bs\sqrt{-j})}{Bs\sqrt{-j}J_0(Bs\sqrt{-j})}. \quad (12)$$

The modelling strategy gives consistent results when compared with experiments also in [2]. The concept of a geometrically sensitive single parameter r which can be defined by a single (repeating) cell then defining the losses is in a sense consistent with Delaney-Bazely-Miki type models [1] where the flow resistivity defines the frequency dependent losses for more random fibrous type absorbent structures.

In this study we consider an absorbent layer 10 cells deep of the form shown in figure 1.2.

The lengths of the individual struts were $375 \mu\text{m}$ with diameters $250 \mu\text{m}$. A one eighth model of the complementary acoustic cavity was geometrically modelled and meshed using gmsh 3.06. This had an open outlet with a forced pressure inlet and a symmetry condition applied to the side walls. No slip and zero acoustic temperature was applied to the curved wetted surface areas. The geometric hydraulic radius r for this structure using equation 6 yielded a value of $400 \mu\text{m}$. The results for the temperature and axial velocity are shown in figure 1.2 and 1.2 for the system running at 1000 Hz.

The computer resources required to model of higher complexity become very expensive, as in addition to the high number of degree of freedom required per node (5) there is also clearly a requirement to locally refine the meshes at the boundaries particularly as the frequencies rise.

Figure 2: Acoustic Temperature

Figure 3: Axial Velocity

Figure 4: Comparison of Cell Models

2 Equivalent Helmholtz Model

A lossy Helmholtz model of the same subsystem was then constructed using an Finite Element model of the equation system following procedures described in [4] ...

$$\omega^2 \frac{\Gamma(\omega)}{K_0} p + \frac{G(\omega)1}{\rho_0} \nabla^2 p = f \quad (13)$$

where the density and bulk modulus are given by 8 and 8. Comparative Padé WCAWE type [5] frequency sweeps of both the Helmholtz system and the full viscothermal model were then run as shown in figure 2.

Two values of r are used for the lossy Helmholtz model. The geometric value of $400 \mu\text{m}$ is shown to underestimate the loss, whilst a tuned value of $270 \mu\text{m}$ generates results which are indistinguishable from the full visco thermal model. The same mesh was used for both systems.

3 Multi-Cell Macro model

The next stage is then to model the full 10 cell structure using the efficient Helmholtz model with the two different values of r . The model is shown in figure 3 and can sustain a uniform mesh structure as there is no specific boundary layer action. A closed boundary condition (hard wall) was implemented on the model end.

This model was also suitable for a WCAWE frequency sweep and the calculated absorbency at inlet is shown in figure 3. Note that no inlet manifold has been included in this model so the blockage effect is directly modelled as a simple area based porosity $\phi = 0.4883$. Thus the inlet impedance was given by

Figure 5: 10 Cell Lossy Helmholtz model

$$Z_i = \frac{p_{inlet}}{\phi \bar{u}_{inlet}} \quad (14)$$

The absorptivity a was then calculated according to ...

$$Ref = \frac{Z_i - \rho_0 c}{Z_i + \rho_0 c} \quad (15)$$

$$a = 1 - |Ref|^2 \quad (16)$$

The sensitivity to the choice of hydraulic radius r values is illustrated in the plot.

4 Experimental Measurements

The relevant ISO standard for the measurement of the acoustical properties of the material is ISO 10534-2:2001. This standard describes the test rig and procedures for estimating the complex acoustic impedance of a material under normal incidence using the "two-microphone" or "transfer function" method. This methodology is used to calculate the reflection and absorption coefficients which are the usual measures used to quantify the performance of an acoustic material.

4.1 Normal Incidence Impedance Tube Testing

In order to facilitate impedance tube testing samples were manufactured using additive techniques. Due to the high resolution and precision required for the material selective laser melting was chosen as the additive manufacturing technology. The 3D Systems Prox DMP 200 was used with the following capabilities:

- Resolution: $x=100 \mu\text{m}$; $y=100 \mu\text{m}$; $z=20 \mu\text{m}$
- Material: metals - Titanium, CoCr, Aluminium, SS
- Build Volume: $x=140 \text{ mm}$; $y=140 \text{ mm}$; $z=125 \text{ mm}$
- Wall Thickness: $150 \mu\text{m}$
- Surface Roughness: Up to $5 \text{ Ra } \mu\text{m}$

Figure 6: Absorbtivity of 10 Cell model

Normal incidence impedance tube tests are used to obtain the reflection factor R and absorption coefficient α , in accordance with the international standard ISO 10534-2:2001. In these tests, the sample is placed in an impedance tube as shown in figure 7 (a), which is taken from the ISO standard. The material is backed by a hard, reflective termination. The custom rig used for this work is also shown in figure 7 (b). In the experimental rig, the hard termination is provided by a 20 mm thick piece of aluminium which can be bolted on the end of the tube.

The cut-on frequency for this tube means that it is only possible to perform tests reliably up to 5050 Hz. The lower limit is determined by the speaker and is in the region of 300 Hz. On the left hand side of figure 7 (b) we can see the BMS 4591 speaker which is driven by the output signal of a National Instruments DAQ which has been amplified by a power amplifier. The box bolts on to the end of the tube to provide a tight seal with little leakage of sound. The square section on the right of figure 7 is the sample holder which opens to hold cylindrical samples of 40 mm diameter and up to 50 mm thick. The sample holder is held shut by four long bolts with wing nuts.

GRAS 40PH array microphones were chosen to instrument the rig as they have a frequency response of 10 Hz - 20 kHz and upper limit of the dynamic range of 135 dB re 20 μPa allowing for testing up to high pressure amplitudes. The microphones are connected to the National Instruments DAQ and the signals are recorded in Matlab. The microphones are calibrated using the switching methods described in the standards to achieve a calibration transfer function which corrects for any differences in the behaviour of the microphones.

The impedance tube requires samples of a 40 mm diameter but due to the periodic structure of the Kelvin cell material a disc of this material will include many partial cells at the edges. These partial cells are impossible to manufacture due to unsupported overhangs in the print so to avoid these the entire sample was printed within a hard wall supporting ring. This hard wall ring was designed to have an inner diameter of 40 mm so as to allow an exact flush fit with the walls of the impedance tube. Custom sample holders were designed to enable this flush fit with the walls of the tube. The sample and holder is shown in figures 8 to 9.

Figure 7: (a) Impedance tube design ISO 10535-2 (b) TCD Impedance tube rig

A comparison of the experimental and numerical results obtained for this test sample are shown in figure 10. Despite the excellent print quality achieved this type of material design pushes current additive manufacturing technologies to their limit. At the time of writing no detailed inspection of the manufactured

Figure 8: CAD of Impedance Tube Sample

Figure 9: Sample attached to build plate manufactured with a 3D Systems Prox DMP 200 and sample in holder for impedance tube testing.

sample has been conducted. However there is promising agreement between the experimental measurement and the numerical simulation. Both sets of results identify a peak absorptivity in the region of 4-4.5 kHz. In general the numerical models have over predicted the achieved experimental absorptivity. Further work will continue to characterise the test sample and attempt to achieve closer agreement in the numerical simulations.

5 Conclusions

The use of a single parameter r to inform density and bulk modulus frequency variations in an efficient equivalent fluid model for the present class of kelvin type meta structure would appear to be a viable proposition to model acoustic losses. The lossy helmholtz model will still retain geometric detail and has thus the potential model gross metabehaviour under more complex loadings.

The use of visco thermal models at a cell level to tune the loss model is a critical part of the procedure and has the further potential to extend the modelling to more detailed local boundary behaviour which can then subsequently be removed from the model in the micro to macro process.

Design optimisation will be facilitated by use of a clearly identifiable geometric parameter. The proposed structure was realised using state of the art additive manufacturing technologies. Initial experimental results conform well the numerical simulations and demonstrate the potential of the approach taken in this work.

Figure 10: Comparison of experimental and numerical results.

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